

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Interim report on first year of Services
Deliverable D4.2**

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

Funded by the European Union. This work has received funding from the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 101093054.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

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ESiWACE3 Deliverable D4.2

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Type:

R - Document, report

Dissemination level:

PU - Public

Delivery date:

M21

Comments:

n/a

Table of contents

Table of contents	4
Introduction	5
Call process	5
Service 1 projects	6
DALES.....	6
GLOBO.....	9
ESMValTool.....	10
OGSTM-BFM.....	13
CAMP.....	15
MESSy.....	20
EC-EARTH4.....	21
Evaluation	22
Conclusion	22

Introduction

As the demand for higher resolution and more accurate weather and climate simulations increases, the need for exascale supercomputers becomes more pressing. Modern (exascale) supercomputers increasingly rely on graphics processing units (GPUs) as the major source of compute power. However, the process of porting existing weather and climate modelling codes to these new systems presents several challenges.

As many existing weather and climate modelling codes are designed to run on traditional CPU-based supercomputers, significant efforts are required to port the codes to new supercomputers and efficiently utilize GPUs. The transition can be difficult for researchers and developers who are accustomed to working with traditional CPU-based systems and may not have experience with programming and optimizing GPU code.

ESiWACE3 Services create collaborative projects that couple developers of weather and climate models with Research Software Engineers (RSEs) who have experience with both HPC and the weather and climate domain. These collaborations last for about a whole year during which the model developers and the research software engineers regularly work together to give guidance and assistance on optimizing and porting weather and climate models to modern HPC systems. This requires a deep understanding of both the weather and climate domain and high performance computing, which is the unique expertise provided by ESiWACE3 engineers. The ESiWACE3 engineers, in close collaboration with the model developers, make substantial modifications to the model source code that advance the model's capability to use modern HPC systems. A crucial factor in ESiWACE3 service projects is that the service project is only granted if the applicant can guarantee that the project will impact the upstream version of the software. This is the version of the code that will be used by countless end users on all kinds of HPC systems across Europe and beyond.

The ESiWACE3 project creates two services. Service 1: "Collaborations to prepare Europe's Weather and Climate Models for pre-exascale systems" focuses on porting and refactoring weather and climate models to new computing architectures, such as GPUs. Service 2: "State-of-the-art development tools for Weather and Climate" focuses on helping weather and climate model developers to adopt the tools developed by ESiWACE3 Work Package 1-3.

This document reports on the 15 months of service projects by presenting and evaluating their achievements, progress and performance, both scientifically and technically.

Call process

The Service 1 and Service 2 calls for proposals are published on the ESiWACE3 website. The call for proposals document¹ gives a detailed description of the purpose of the calls, what can be applied for, who can apply, how to prepare an application, and specific conditions that apply to the calls.

The assessment procedure is also explained in detail in the call for proposals document. The proposals are reviewed in two phases. First, a technical feasibility and software sustainability check is performed. This technical review decides which proposals make it to round 2, the scientific review. A scientific review committee is established for each round of proposals to be

¹ <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/software-support/esiwace3-2024-service1-cfp.pdf>

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D4.2

evaluated, comprising established researchers in the weather and climate community, both internal and external to the ESiWACE consortium, who take the final granting decision based on scientific relevance, importance to the community, and potential scientific impact of the work.

This report was written in September 2024, Month 21 (M21) of the ESiWACE3 project. So far, we have held 3 calls for Service proposals. The table below shows the total number of applications per call and the names of the projects that have been accepted in this call.

Date of Service 1 call closing	Submitted proposals	Accepted proposals
28-06-2023	4 in total	DALES, GLOBO, ESMValTool
01-11-2023	6 in total	OGSTM-BFM, CAMP, MESSy, EC-EARTH4 (started in July 2024)
03-06-2024	5 in total	Wflow, Trixi, NEMO

Service 2 was scheduled to start one year after the start of Service 1, so in Month 18 of the project. As such, only one call for Service 2 projects has been organized so far. The Service 2 call was requesting proposals on the use of the AutoRPE, Spack, and Kernel Tuner tools. Two proposals have been received for the Service 2 call, one on Spack and one on Kernel Tuner. The proposal on the use of Spack has been rejected, because it did not fit the scope of the call. The proposal on using Kernel Tuner to optimize models with mixed-precision techniques on GPUs has been accepted and the project is scheduled to start in September 2024.

The following section presents a status update of the work performed so far in the running Service 1 projects. Do note that these are not final results and several projects have only recently started.

Service 1 projects

This section gives an overview of the achievements, progress and performance made and obtained during 15 months (from M6 to M21) by the currently granted Service 1 projects. Note that the projects are still running and work in some projects has only just started. The newly granted Service 1 projects are not included, because work on those projects will start late 2024 (after this deliverable was written).

DALES

The Dutch Atmospheric Large Eddy Simulation DALES is a Fortran90 program designed to model atmospheric processes at high resolution, such as clouds, convection, precipitation and turbulence. DALES includes the optional transport and reactions of chemical compounds and is linked to the external RRTMG radiation library.

The aim of this service project is to port DALES to GPUs using OpenACC. Recently, this effort has been initiated by the DALES developers for non-precipitating cases excluding radiation. The goal of this service was to extend and improve the GPU implementation to include more realistic situations, by (a) porting microphysics schemes to GPUs and (b) performing the radiation computation on the GPU.

Figure 1: Baseline situation before work was started. Single-GPU weak scaling of the DALES Bomex dry physics test case, comparing a regular compute node (EPYC 7H12) to a single NVidia A100 chip. Test was performed on the Dutch national supercomputer Snellius.

In this period, we have interfaced DALES with the radiation software RTE-RRTMGP (<https://github.com/earth-system-radiation/rte-rtmgp>), which exploits fine-grained parallelisation of radiation calculations and features multi-GPU calculations through OpenACC. Comparing CPU and GPU computational times for a given problem size on a node basis (192 AMD CPU against 4 Nvidia A100), the GPU implementation speeds up radiation calculations by a factor of 7.

In parallel, we have ported the simple and bulk microphysics schemes to GPUs using OpenACC and implemented the DALES restarting functionality for GPU-resident runs. This allowed us to perform realistic runs featuring all relevant physical processes. Performance has been assessed on different hardware, namely NVIDIA A100 and H100 cards and is currently being benchmarked on an AMD MI250x at LUMI. As a result, we observe acceleration of the different physical processes with factors between $\sim 4x$ and $\sim 10x$ (see Fig. 2). We also experimented further optimisations with Kernel Tuner, an auto-tuning GPU application.

Figure 2: Speedup per subroutine for the DALES GPU code running the Cloud Botany test case. The CPU baseline was done on a full AMD Epyc Genoa node.

In addition to testing the single node performances, we investigated DALES weak scaling performances from 1 to 64 GPUs. Leveraging the periodicity of the test case, the computational domain size is increased by a factor two in each dimension while reusing the same initial data, ensuring a constant work per GPUs. Figure 3. shows that the overall DALES weak scaling efficiency drops quickly past a single node, mostly driven by the poor performances of the Poisson solver which requires all-to-all communications. In contrast, radiation, thermodynamics and microphysics exhibit near perfect scaling efficiency in the range of problem sizes tested.

Figure 3: Weak scaling of DALES on Snellius NVidia A100 nodes, from 1 to 64 GPUs, along with per subroutine scaling efficiency.

All the methodology and results have been summarized in a submitted conference paper, to be presented at the IPDPS 2025 conference in the spring 2025. Further work on DALES could focus on improving scaling performances by exploring alternative solvers to perform the low Mach number projection, such as alternative Poisson transposition pattern or multigrid solvers out of the Hypre library.

GLOBO

GLOBO is an atmospheric general circulation model developed at the Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate (ISAC) (CNR, Italy). GLOBO is currently used as a research tool for predictability studies on different time scales ranging from the short range to the subseasonal scale. It is also used as an operational forecasting tool to provide, on a daily basis, a 7-day global forecast and initial and boundary conditions for higher resolution regional models, and, on a weekly basis, a 32-day ensemble forecast.²

The specific objective of this collaboration is to improve the exploration of multi core HPC resources and study the identified specific bottlenecks related to parallelization of I/O operations or any other optimization that would pave the way for a future GPU-acceleration of the GLOBO model.

The code was ported to Atos' internal cluster and the build system adapted for several compilers including an *ifort* toolchain. This showed a difference in performance of about 25% in favor of *ifort* compared to the *gfortran* toolchain that is usually used. Profiling indicates this comes mostly from better vectorization. A major part of the execution resides inside MPI communications with a significant imbalance between the master processor and others.

The scripted build system of GLOBO has been replaced by a recent and modern approach based on CMake. This leads to a 5 to 90 times faster compilation without any sequential phase or erroneous file dependencies. A first optimization has also been applied by inlining a function leading to a 15% improvement thanks to a better vectorization from the compiler.

The I/O operations have been modified by introducing the parallel writing of the NetCDF library for the output files. The input file readings were also modified to use the MPI IO functions to read the MDHF and GEO files. With the big test case, the files are relatively small, around 300MB, so the results are difficult to characterize. The timings of the parallel and the sequential implementations are similar but now GLOBO is able to switch between the two.

The next steps will be to work on the imbalance between the processors as the last profiling shows in the trace that few processors compute while others are waiting.

² <https://www.isac.cnr.it/dinamica/projects/forecasts/>

ESMValTool

The Earth System Model Evaluation Tool³ (Eyring et al., 2020) is a community-developed, open-source software tool for the evaluation and analysis of output from ESMs. For example, it allows comparing output of single or multiple models against results from previous versions or against re-analyses and observations. ESMValTool provides diagnostics for several different realms (e.g., atmosphere, ocean, land, etc.), and is developed with contributions of over 200 developers from more than 60 international institutions.

The goal of this project is to optimize the code path of standard workflows in ESMValTool and improve the data loading speed of ESMValTool on various high-end supercomputers, such as the Levante system at DKRZ. A secondary goal is to allow object-stored climate data as input for the tool, to make a connection to the Pangeo community.

ESMValCore, the framework running ESMValTool workflows, comes with approximately 60 'preprocessor' functions. These are functions that perform common tasks, such as regridding and computing statistics, that are used by many of the workflows. An important step in achieving good computational performance is to make sure these functions use Dask arrays instead of plain Numpy arrays. Dask arrays facilitate out-of-core computations, resulting in lower minimum memory requirements, thereby enabling the analysis of larger datasets. An added benefit is improved parallelism, leading to faster analyses. A major outcome of this project is that 55 preprocessor functions are now compatible with Dask arrays and work is in progress on another 4. This effort has resulted in a performance benefit for the bulk of the ESMValTool recipes, as shown in Figure 1. A few recipes have displayed a performance regression, which is likely due to the high complexity and poor parallelism of the Dask task graph.

Figure 1: Sorted speedups obtained for ESMValTool v2.11 (May 2024) vs v2.10 (December 2023), each bar representing a distinct standard ESMValTool recipe, measured using the Dask default scheduler on a single DKRZ Levante compute node.

In addition to the work on the preprocessor functions, we have profiled two distinct use cases ('recipes') of the ESMValTool, representing both coarse-scale IPCC-ready CMIP6 multi-model analyses on climatological time scales (see Figure 2) and shorter seasonal processing jobs for

³ <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-13-3383-2020>

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D4.2

high-resolution climate data. We have identified several potential bottlenecks, often stemming from redundant loading of (poorly chunked) metadata from disk in the underlying Iris library. We have removed many of these bottlenecks and improved parallelism wherever possible. This resulted in the speedups shown in Table 1. For the IPCC multi-model test case, which requires about 1200 input files with a total size of 90 GB, most of the time is spent in metadata computations which are still performed mostly sequentially. Therefore this recipe is unlikely to benefit from running it on multiple nodes. The high-resolution recipe, which requires only 200 input files with a total size of 700 GB, is as expected, much more scalable due to the relatively small footprint of sequential metadata reads and writes. We have developed a prototype with improved parallelism for metadata computations, but this requires additional work because one of the underlying libraries (ESMF/ESMPy) is not (yet) compatible with Dask.

recipe type	Speed-up 1 node	Speed-up 2 nodes	Speed-up 4 nodes
IPCC multi-model	4	-	-
high-resolution	5	7	10

Table 1: Speed-up factors compared to the baseline at the start of the project using a Dask cluster consisting of nodes from the DKRZ Levante "compute" partition. Each node has 128 CPU cores and 256 GB of RAM and data is stored on a Lustre filesystem.

Figure 2: flame graph of the CMIP6 multi-model analysis script, with several redundant metadata calculation sections highlighted in red. Test performed at DKRZ Levante system, with data on the Lustre scratch file system.

OGSTM-BFM

OGSTM-BFM is a transport reaction model applied to marine biogeochemistry used both for process study on the marine ecosystem, short term forecast and climate projection, developed by the BFM consortium⁴.

The main objective of the project is to port on GPU the different routines of OGSTM and BFM. The developers have identified several important routines, the complex carbonate equations solving routine from BFM, and the horizontal and vertical diffusion routines from OGSTM. All these objectives have been met, leaving more time for GPU porting and optimisations. We are confident we will be able to fully port OGSTM-BFM on GPU by the end of the project and do a basic optimisation pass on the code. With reference to Figure 1, for now we have reached a speedup of about 6.5 compared to the old GPU version but data transfers are still a major bottleneck. By porting more code on GPU we will be able to only transfer data back to CPU when dumping output to disk. We still expect MPI communications to be a significant bottleneck and we don't know whether we will be able to optimize this aspect within the project timeframe.

Figure 1: Nsight Systems trace showing original GPU port status (at the top) compared to the current GPU port status (on the bottom). We can already see a speedup factor of 6.5, time being dominated by data transfers (shown in green and purple at the top).

⁴ <https://bfm-community.github.io/www.bfm-community.eu/#documentation>

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D4.2

We were able to assist the developers with deploying OGSTM-BFM on the Leonardo supercomputer while fixing a boundary conditions bug. We managed to do a thorough validation of the numerical results and no numerical anomalies remain in the current output produced.

In the figure 2 we show the current CPU version on Milan processors with 128 MPI processes (in blue) against the current GPU version on 4 A100 GPU and Milan processor, with 1 and 2 processes per GPU (in respectively green and purple). We can see that the current GPU speedup is fairly modest but we still need to port more code sections with OpenACC. We also show a speedup prediction of about 6 where we removed the data transfers between CPU and GPU as we expect to be able to remove them for the most part. It shall serve as a minimal goal to achieve for the remaining effort and time planned for the project (3PM).

Figure 2: Node performance comparison between CPU and GPU version of OGSTM-BFM.

CAMP

Introduction

Chemistry Across Multiple Phases (CAMP) is a software for a flexible treatment for gas- and aerosol-phase chemical processes for incorporation in models of diverse scales, from box models up to global Earth System models. Key features of this novel framework are (i) an abstracted aerosol representation that allows a chemical mechanism to be solved on models with different aerosol representations (e.g., binned, modal, or particle-resolved), (ii) a run-time model configuration through a combination of JSON input files, and (iii) a flexible implementation in heterogeneous CPU/GPU architectures. CAMP has been deployed in the particle-resolved PartMC model and the Multiscale Online Atmosphere Chemistry (MONARCH) chemical weather prediction system for use at regional and global scales.

The primary goal is to revise and optimize the GPU implementation of the code in Marenostrom 5. The GPU implementation of CAMP includes deep optimization development, which is a step forward from the current community approach of just translating the code to GPU, even when the algorithm and data distribution are optimized for a CPU environment but not so much for the highly parallel GPU architecture. This work can benefit the community by quantifying the performance achieved by expending some extra time on applying the optimizations performed, in addition to being used as the basis for hardware acceleration of numerous geoscientific models that rely on atmospheric chemical kinetics applications. Significantly it can directly benefit the models and scientist groups where CAMP is currently deployed.

Methodology

Overall, we upgraded the CAMP solver to run simultaneously on both CPU and GPU architectures. We included a new load-balancing algorithm to improve the usage of both architectures compared to manually setting the balance. We present a performance analysis of the CPU version for future optimizations.

We include significant improvements to the GPU execution, such as reducing data transfers by a factor of 4x, which contributes to the acceleration. The load-balancing algorithm adjusts the load for each chemistry time step based on the distribution from the previous time step. The algorithm is designed to stabilize at the optimal load balance, where the CPU and GPU times are nearly equal. The algorithm's code is open source and compressed into less than a hundred lines, facilitating future porting to other software. We define a metric to quantify the achieved load balance (ideal load balance at 100%) as follows:

$$LoadBalance[\%] = Avg(100 * \frac{\min(timeGPU, timeCPU)}{\max(timeGPU, timeCPU)})$$

Where *Avg* represents the average load balance across different time steps, *timeCPU* corresponds to the time taken by the CPU-related code, and *timeGPU* includes the time of the data transfers between CPU and GPU, the kernel execution, and the waiting time for the GPU to finish.

Test configuration

The hardware used is the recent Marenostrom 5 cluster (<https://www.bsc.es/marenostrom/marenostrom-5>). We also compare the previous results from Marenostrom 4. The CPU-GPU and CPU-Only versions were tested on the ACC and GPP partitions.

The chemistry configuration corresponds to the gas-phase mechanism Carbon Bond 2005 (CB05). The mechanism and domain details are in the CAMP v1.0 paper (<https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/15/3663/2022/>). The settings of the CAMP solver, such as the solver algorithm or tolerance, are detailed in the CAMP GPU thread-block paper

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0010465524001632>). The paper details the “Box model” test for CPU profiling and the speedup against 1 GPU core. The rest of the measures are taken from running CAMP on MONARCH in a 1-day simulation. The GPU profiling is obtained using the Nsight Compute tool.

CPU profiling

CAMP CPU (also called the Box model) contains a CPU implementation that uses a distributed-memory approach using the MPI library. It is entirely parallel, which means that the domain is decomposed at the beginning of the execution into many subdomains, called cells, and all the computation happens without any dependencies, synchronization, or communication between tasks. We have used Extrae and Paraver, from the BSC toolset, as the main tools to perform this profiling analysis.

Top-consuming user functions

The CAMP dwarf iterates over the requested timesteps calling the *integrate* user function. The first approach was to trace *integrate* to check the time of each timestep. Figure 1 shows a Paraver trace view with 10 tasks and 5 timesteps (tasks in the x-axis and timeline on the y-axis), where green flags mark the start and end of each timestep.

Figure 1: Trace view of the user functions.

Timesteps are irregular, as not all the steps take the same time. The workload of the computations also seems irregular, as each task takes a different time to complete all the computations. This can be an effect of a convergent algorithm of the timesteps or a bad workload distribution.

More user functions were profiled to measure the elapsed time, as shown in the Paraver histogram of Figure 2. Around 80% of the time is spent in the CNode and cvDlsSetup user functions, so we have to ensure their computational performance is good. The Avg/Max metric of the histogram (average by maximum) measures the degree of imbalance, with 1 being a completely balanced application. A value above 0.8 is acceptable.

User functions histogram @ usr fx steps 10 100000 5.prv							
	CNode	cvDlsSetup	End	camp_mon..tegrate_	cvDlsSolve	cvEwtSet	CNodeSetInitStep
Total	403.20 %	372.71 %	133.57 %	54.76 %	27.31 %	8.39 %	0.07 %
Average	40.32 %	37.27 %	13.36 %	5.48 %	2.73 %	0.84 %	0.01 %
Maximum	45.30 %	43.72 %	26.36 %	5.72 %	3.20 %	0.95 %	0.01 %
Minimum	34.71 %	30.76 %	2.70 %	5.27 %	2.15 %	0.67 %	0.01 %
StDev	3.38 %	4.07 %	7.71 %	0.13 %	0.34 %	0.10 %	0.00 %
Avg/Max	0.89	0.85	0.51	0.96	0.85	0.88	0.88

Figure 2: Histogram with percentage of elapsed time for the profiled user functions.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D4.2

We also checked the number of calls to each user function for each MPI task, which varies. This suggests that it is a convergent algorithm, which has a natural imbalance above an acceptable threshold.

Performance counters

Some hardware metrics available on MN5 were also analyzed, including instructions per cycle (IPC), cache misses, and vectorization ratio.

CAMP CPU has a good performance regarding IPC (around 4) and cache misses (70 L1 misses per 1000 instructions). However, the vectorization ratio is not good, revealing that the vectorization of the top-consuming user functions is bad. According to the vectorization report of the Intel compiler, 210 loops were not vectorized due to different reasons.

GPU results

Table 1 shows that we have doubled the speedup against the single thread CPU version compared to the Marenostrom 4 version (e.g., from 137x to 250x). We consider this a significant improvement.

Version	N° of GPUs	Speedup
Marenostrom 5	1-4	70-250
Marenostrom4	1-4	31-137

Table 1: Speedup using 1 and 4 GPUs against 1 CPU core. The Marenostrom 4 version was GPU-Only, while the Marenostrom 5 is the CPU-GPU version.

Table 2 shows that the load balance in the automatic case is 3% lower compared to the fixed load case. However, the speedup is higher, resulting in 8.14x, 1.25 times faster than the fixed configuration.

Load to GPU [%]	Speedup	Error	Load balance [%]
Fixed	6.51	0.56	61
Automatic	8.14	0.59	58

Table 2: In a node-against-node comparison, Speedup, error, and load balance against the CPU version. The Fixed case computes 85% of the load to the GPU for the whole execution, while the Automatic is initially set to 95% and changes for each chemistry time step.

Normalizing the number of cores of the Marenostrom 4 and 5 clusters, the CPU-GPU Marenostrom 5 version is 2.32x faster than the GPU-Only Marenostrom 4 version.

Figure 3 shows that Marenostrom 5 increases the utilization of SMs and Memory by 5% and 28%, respectively, compared to Marenostrom 4. We attribute this improvement to the higher capabilities of the Marenostrom 5 GPU, which has more SMs and Memory available to handle the high computational load.

Figure 3: Utilization of GPU resources. The first (blue), second (green), and third (purple) bars correspond to the versions CPU-GPU Marenostrom 5, GPU-Only Marenostrom 4, and GPU-only Marenostrom 5, respectively.

Figure 4 shows that Marenostrom 5 exhibits approximately 9x times more performance and 6x higher Arithmetic Intensity than Marenostrom 4, underscoring the advantages of the newer GPU. However, the Arithmetic Intensity decreases by 3x in the CPU-GPU version compared to the GPU-only version. The cause of this decline is attributed to the numerous code changes implemented, which indicates there is potential for further improvement.

Figure 4: Roofline model. The performance bound is represented by the blue curve. Starting from the left, the first and second points are single floating point operations, while the rest are double. The third, fourth, and fifth points correspond to versions GPU-Only Marenostrom 4, CPU-GPU Marenostrom 5, and GPU-Only Marenostrom 5. We are interested in doubles.

The cache L1 and L2 hit rates improved from 82% and 99% in the GPU-Only version to 92% and 99% in the CPU-GPU version. This enhancement is attributed to using the CSR sparse structure instead of the CSC structure in the GPU-only version.

Conclusions

We introduced a parallel CPU-GPU implementation and a simple and effective automatic load-balancing algorithm. This approach integrates the GPU and CPU solvers into an asynchronous execution model, enabling concurrent computation of the workload by both processors.

The CPU-GPU version in the “Box model” test reports a 70x speedup against the single-thread CPU version using a single GPU. Increasing the GPUs to 4, the speedup scales to 250x. This

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D4.2

speedup doubles the previous results from the GPU-Only Marenostrom 4 version. The MONARCH results show that the automatic load balance outperforms the fixed load balance by 25%, achieving a total speedup of 8.14x in a node-to-node comparison. The normalized speedup against the GPU-Only version is 2.32x. This notable enhancement underscores the advantages of the heterogeneous implementation, particularly with optimizations such as reduced CPU-GPU data transfers.

MESSy

The Modular Earth Submodel System (MESSy)⁵ is a software project providing an infrastructure for coupling atmospheric models (e.g., ICON, ECHAM, COSMO) and specialized ESM components, the so-called submodels (e.g., physical parameterizations, chemistry packages, diagnostics) via generalized interfaces for standardized control and coupling. MESSy will be ported to GPU submodel wise. As MESSy contains some computationally expensive process implementations, speedup on the process level can be taken as granted. However, if only individual processes are ported, frequent copies of high amounts of data between host and device will diminish the gain in speed substantially. In order to accelerate the model as soon and as much as possible, i.e. already during the porting process, the data transfer between host and device needs to be optimized, so that the speedup of individual code sections can be decoupled from the memory update.

Due to unexpected staff shortages, the work could only be started much later than planned. The collaboration with the MESSy developers has been adjusted accordingly. After initial problems in the provided setup were fixed together with the MESSy development team, full-scale work started in July 2024. As one of the first steps, a CI pipeline was set up to automatically check the development work for any errors. Detailed profiling was also very helpful for further planning. The profiling process was performed on the Levante HPC system (Figure 5). The next step is to move the SEDI submodule with the DWARF base model to the GPU and develop a strategy for data movement before running it with ICON.

Figure 5: Nsight Systems profile showing the current data movement of already ported MESSy submodel (Top). Score-P profiling (Bottom) showing in CubeGUI the total run time of the program on CPU and GPU. It can be seen that GPUs have slower timing due to the frequent data transfer for approx. 23%.

⁵ <https://messy-interface.org/>

EC-EARTH4

EC-Earth is an Earth system model developed by a European consortium of national meteorological services and research institutes. The EC-Earth consortium was started in 2006 and has welcomed many new partners ever since. By now, EC-Earth has become a prominent state-of-the-art model within the international landscape of global climate and Earth system models. The EC-Earth consortium has contributed to the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP), and will continue to do so in the future. EC-Earth is also used as a research tool in various national, European and international projects.

The goal of this project is to have the M7 aerosols module running in mixed precision in OpenIFS 48r1, which will be the atmospheric component of the new EC-Earth 4. However, some preliminary steps were needed before we could start working on this, which consisted in integrating the M7 module into OpenIFS 48r1. They finally managed to come up with a tagged OpenIFS+M7 version during this summer, which they think is suitable to start this project. We have already scheduled a meeting for this month between KNMI and BSC to discuss the next steps, define a work plan, among other useful aspects to succeed in the completion of the project within the next 12 months.

Evaluation

This report assesses how the ESiWACE3 services are running overall. There have been several challenges that we have encountered in Service 1, in particular with regard to staffing. The CAMP and MESSy projects have both been delayed due to staffing issues at BSC and DKRZ, respectively. Fortunately, these positions have now been filled and the service projects are up and running again.

In terms of the reach of the services, we still see that the service applications are mostly received from the direct network of ESiWACE3 partners, in particular from the Netherlands, France, Germany, and Spain, which means that our communication towards the wider European community can and should be improved further.

Due to Service 2 being highly specialized towards certain tools, it is expected that the number of applications is lower than for Service 1. Nonetheless, we have identified some improvements with regard to how Service 2 is advertised. For example, on the website there is visually very little distinction between Service 1 and Service 2, while the two services serve different purposes and possibly even different audiences. As such, we plan to improve the way in which Service 2 is advertised to highlight how it differs from Service 1.

In terms of progress, the evaluation is positive. Indeed, the projects are progressing well as one can see with the presented status and early results.

Conclusion

In summary, we have organized three calls for Service 1 projects and one call for Service 2 projects in the first 21 months of ESiWACE. After some staffing shortages in the first year, the first two sets granted Service 1 projects are currently up and running. Three newly granted projects will be able to start before the end of the year. As explained above, we have identified a few areas where we can improve, in particular related to communication and dissemination. While most service projects are still underway, we can already see that the performance of several applications is significantly improving, as is their capability to efficiently utilize modern HPC systems, including EuroHPC systems like Marenostrum 5 (BSC⁶) and Leonardo (CINECA⁷), and other national GPU clusters like Levante at DKRZ⁸ and Snellius at SURF⁹, thanks to the collaborations between RSEs and weather and climate modeling communities created by the ESiWACE3 Services.

⁶ <https://www.bsc.es/ca/marenostrum/marenostrum-5>

⁷ <https://leonardo-supercomputer.cineca.eu/>

⁸ <https://docs.dkrz.de/doc/levante/index.html>

⁹ <https://www.surf.nl/en/services/snellius-the-national-supercomputer>